
The Effect of Indigenous People of Biafra’s Agitation on Academic Activities in Tertiary Institutions in Ebonyi State: A study of Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana

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ABSTRACT	ARTICLE DETAILS
<p>The problems of insecurity in southeast geo-political zone especially the sit at home order are affecting the educational institutions. Based on this, this paper discussed effect of Biafra’s agitations on academic activities of tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State: A study of Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana. Among other things discussed included the concept of sit at home order, effect of Biafra agitation on the academic activities of tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State: A study of Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana. The research used descriptive method to analyse the effect of Biafra’s agitation on academic activities in tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State: The paper concluded by recommending that : In order to reduce political instability, the nation should hold a referendum on IPOB's request for self-determination, Saturday schooling should be revoked to cushion the effect of the agitation in the state, Federal Government should adhere to federal character principle in political appointments and True federalism should be practiced in Nigeria by the federal government in order to carry all the ethnic groups along because Nigeria is vast</p> <p>KEYWORDS: Agitation, Biafra, Ebony State, Education, Sit-At-Home Order.</p>	<p>Published On: 03 June 2026</p> <p>Available on: https://ijiissh.com/</p>

INTRODUCTION

Biafra agitation as a topic is a very difficult and emotional one. The commemoration of Nigeria's civil war experience is still a contentious issue. After the military took control of political leadership in 1966, the former Eastern Region – predominantly made up of Igbo people and one of the three major ethnic groupings of Nigeria – proclaimed herself the ‘Republic of Biafra.’ This led to Nigeria’s civil war. More so, this experience has continued to influence Nigerian politics. In the recent years, the country has witnessed neo-Biafran movements, a coalition of some Igbo speaking Nigerians who claim to be Biafrans rather than Nigerians (Brown and Oghabgonbgon 2016). Repeated calls for the independence of the states of the South-East and some in the South-South zone of Nigeria led to the resurrection of Biafra agitation in 2015. The agitation began during the 1967–1970 civil war in Nigeria. After the civil war, the area was re-annexed to Nigeria, but this did not halt the agitation. Instead, it sparked the creation of many pro-Biafra movements in the zone. The first ‘formalized’ vehicle for articulating the agitation was established in September 1999 with the founding of the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB) (Meshach and Fanen 2020). Economic activities in the areas where these protests take place are frequently disrupted by the Biafra activists' regular demonstrations and fights with the security forces. Apart from the disruption of economic activities, Biafra protests in Nigeria generally and in the South-East specifically may deter Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). Biafra agitation may be attributed to leadership failure, which resulted in years of social neglect, economic isolation, and political exclusion of Nigerians, especially those from the South-East. The issue is made worse by the failure of successive governments to address the high unemployment rate, corruption, and improper use of public monies that conflict with the interests of the country. This study focuses on the effect of Biafra’s agitation on academic activities in tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State: A study of Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana

Concept of Sit at Home Order

Sit at home order is a strategy adopted by non-state actors to press for the releasing of their president arrested by the Nigerian government. Sit at home order is a threat action to force the government to release their leader that was arrested by the Nigerian

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government. Sit at home order is an order of restriction given within a region and enforcing illegally by non-state actors to violently demands the release of their leader from the Nigerian government. The Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) first introduced the sit-at-home order in the Southeast to add pressure to their quest for the actualization of an independent nation of Biafra and to show that most people in the Southeast support their quest for freedom. It soon transformed into a tool for achieving other goals, including raising of awareness for other Biafran-related issues and, of recent, it has become a tool to draw attention to the plight of the leader of IPOB, Nnamdi Kanu. Ugwe, (2022) reported that in August, 2021, IPOB introduced the order to put pressure on the Nigerian government to release its leader, Nnamdi Kanu, who is standing trial before the Federal High Court, Abuja, for treason and terrorism. He went further to observed that IPOB initially declared the holiday for Mondays but later extended it to every day Mr Kanu appears in court. Since then, the South-east has become a ghost region with all businesses shut down on such days and every Monday as residents stay at home, mainly out of fear of attack. Gunmen have been attacking traders and commuters across the region who flouts the order. They have killed many people and set ablaze goods worth millions of naira for being sold or transported on such days.

RATIONALE FOR BIAFRA AGITATION.

1. Ethnic Dissection and Competition

The current agitation for Biafra is led by the Igbo masses who feel disappointed by the failure of their elite to capture federal power. The current agitation for Biafra "represents a complete fracture between the Igbo elite and their masses" due to the inability of the former to capture the Nigerian presidency, and suggests that "the fact of the matter is that the Igbo elite has a strong empirical basis to read Nigerian political history as one of failure and frustration for them... With this failure of the elite, the Igbos have seized the initiative of following the path of disintegration".

2. Economic Marginalization

In Nigeria's politics today, issues bordering on economic participation always take the centre stage. Discourse on national issues are not without reference to words like, 'fiscal federalism', 'derivation formula', revenue sharing, etc. because of the centralized nature of revenue generation and distribution among the three tiers of government. The constituent tiers of government rely heavily on revenue from the central government to meet their budgetary expenses, including salaries of workers. Since the early 1970s, the main focus of political agitation in the South-South has been revenue allocation. Individuals, associations and governments of the oil producing states have been campaigning for a greater share of the country's oil wealth. Derivation (allocating revenue in a way that returns a high proportion of revenue to the region or state where it is derived) was a major principle of both vertical and horizontal revenue allocation in Nigeria before the 1970s... This was the period when solid minerals (mainly tin and coal) and export crops were the leading sources of revenue.

3. State Society Relations

The persistence of Biafra separatist agitation also links it to the nature of state-society relations in Nigeria. The re-emergence of Biafra separatism is traceable to the opening up of Nigeria's political space following the country's transition to democracy in 1999. Since 1999, Nigeria's political space has been diversified following the entrance of new non-state actors, such as ethno-nationalist movements, into that space. The post-1999 political space is characterized by "confrontation between state-led nationalism and state-seeking nationalism [led by non-state actors]." In the contest, the state-seeking nationalists appear to be losing out to the hegemonic state led nationalist project, prompting a change of strategy by ethno-nationalist groups and intensification of the demands for alternative spaces and parallel structures of power. The result of these developments is increase in separatist agitation.

4. Political Marginalization

As things stand presently, there are some segments of the country that still feel that the political power structure of the nation is lopsided and therefore favours others against themselves. But whether this is the case and meets the threshold of exclusion and oppression to qualify for self-determination remains to be seen, as the ensuing portion of this work amply demonstrates. The intriguing nature of power 'rotation' in Nigeria has basically quieted some interest groups and their demand for secession. The entire southern part of the country on return to democracy in 1999 insisted that the North had had more than a fair share of political power and it was time it moved to one of the regions in the southern part of the country.

5 Expiration of Nigeria's Amalgamation Proclamation and Restoration of the Sovereign State of Biafra

In 1914, the British Government under the recommendation of Frederick Lugard amalgamated the southern and northern regions of areas bordering with Cameroon, Chad, Niger, and Benin republic, and proclaimed the amalgamated geo-space as a country with the name Nigeria. This amalgamation was executed without the consent of the indigenous people that constituted these. According to the proclamation documents, the amalgamation was conditioned to have a lifespan of 100 years (expiring on December 31, 2013) after which any of the amalgamating regions or peoples would have the right to opt out. For the past 100 years, the indigenous people of Biafra who are part of the constituents of Nigeria have suffered untold hardship, threats to their culture, tradition and their

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way of life combined with political and economic emasculation, and annihilation of her citizens by the Hausa/Fulani-Yoruba dominated Nigerian government. The Indigenous People of Biafra resolved not to extend the amalgamation and thereby stated that Nigeria ceases as a legal corporate entity which represents the Indigenous People of Biafra in any capacity from the 1st of January 2014.

6. Insecurity and State Failure

When a particular ethnic group feels that they do not have a stake in the future of an existing political unit they may tend to agitate for their own political unit. This is especially so where the political entity has failed socially, economically and politically. To illustrate state failure by focusing on Nigeria, the government seems to be helpless to prevent or adequately respond to the frequent killing and destruction of lives and properties in Nigeria. This leads to questions on the ability of Nigeria's national security to function proactively. The inability of the Nigerian government to resolve the agitations in "South South", "South East", the herdsmen and farmers' conflicts and Boko Haram in the North East, kidnappings and abductions, among others, serve as good examples through which to examine the inefficiency and lack of trust which are the tenets of state failure.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The main objective of this research is to examine the effect of Biafra's agitation on academic activities in tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State: A study of Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana

METHODOLOGY

The research makes use of descriptive method to analyse the effect of Biafra's agitation on academic activities in tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State: A study of Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana.

Study Area (Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana in Afikpo-North Local Government Area, Ebonyi State.)

Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana was established in 1981 as the first federal polytechnic in Southeast Nigeria. It was first located in a temporary site at the Federal Government College, Okposi in Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria and moved to its permanent site in Unwana in 1987.

In 1982, a foundation stone for a permanent site was laid at Unwana in Afikpo-North Local Government Area, Ebonyi State. In the same year the first class of students were admitted to pursue various programs leading to the award of National Diploma (ND) and Higher National Diploma (HND) in science, engineering, and humanities. The polytechnic operates five schools in eighteen departments and has programs leading to National Diploma (ND) and Higher National Diploma (HND) in sciences, engineering, and humanities.

Empirical Review

According to the results of a study by Yetunde et al. (2022), Nigeria is a vulnerable state. This fragility exposes the central government's weakness or incapacity to exert effective control over a large portion of its territory, as well as the under-provision of public services, widespread corruption, criminal activities, refugees, forcible population displacement, and sharp economic decline. A study by Eric (2021) was carried out to examine Biafra agitation, focusing on the factors that led to the current resurgence of the agitation. According to the study, the contemporary Biafra agitation is built on systemic problems such as marginalization, economic inequality, social alienation, ethnic suspicion, and subordination. The study recommended that the Biafra debacle may be resolved by the deployment of peacekeepers and peace builders, as well as through the use of various peacemaking measures, such as negotiation, mediation, settlement, and diplomatic channels. The study also suggested three layers of conflict resolution involving Biafra separatist movements, conflict resolution between the Nigerian government and the Biafra agitators, and multi-track diplomacy to engage all ethnic groups, particularly the Hausa-Fulani Muslims and the Igbo Christians. A different study by Ada, Seyi and Mojibola (2020) looked at the history of the Igbo people in Nigeria, their position and self-determination movement, as well as the federal government's responses to their agitation over time. The researchers came to the conclusion that the Igbo position is one of the nation's most unifying concerns that the government has failed to address. They accepted that the right to self-determination is inalienable but insisted that any group seeking self government must adhere to the law and not use it as a vehicle for attention, self promotion, or political sabotage.

Another study that was conducted to determine the cause of Biafra's persistent agitation in Nigeria despite government efforts to put an end to the agitations at various points in time was done by (Mohammed & Shuaibu, 2019). The study was based on the use of social media networks by the agitators to convey their messages to the wider world. The study employed Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) with a sociolinguistic foundation to examine how sociolinguistic concepts like virtual community, identity, linguistic variety, and social interaction are projected to represent self-determination and the pursuit of political independence. Based on the findings, increased internet-enabled devices that are pervasive in modern culture are encouraging the Igbo people to gradually

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mobilize themselves for the Biafra agenda through social media. According to this study, the country's unity is under risk due to the continuous push for self-government by the Igbo people.

Furthermore, a study was done to examine the reasons for popular movements, specifically MASSOB's and IPOB's demand for self-determination in opposition to the Nigerian state's position on the matter (Osaghae, 2017). The study discovered that the incapacity of the Nigerian state to place the people's sense of belonging at the center is what has caused these recurrent calls for self-determination. The researcher denounced the use of military force and the legal system as the means of resolving conflicts in Nigeria that have ethnic and religious overtones. According to him, these strategies will more likely result in further escalation of the conflict. This is because military intervention and the subsequent retributive justice may not have the resources to identify the covert grievances. These are what fuel the conflict (Osaghae, 2017). Due to this, the researcher suggested a paradigm shift from coercive policy to mediation and discussion and from retributive policy to restorative justice.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK – INSTRUMENTALISM

For the purpose of this study, the instrumentalism theory has been adopted as the theoretical framework on which the study is based. The theory of instrumentalism emphasizes on flexibility of ethnic sentiments that depend on circumstance and the choice of the individual. The theory of political instrumentalism attributes the outbreak of inter-group conflict to ethnic entrepreneurs who capitalize on the availability of ethnic networks to mobilize masses along ethnic lines. This especially occurs when political elites are in danger of being 'ethnically outbid' by extremists or when domestic or international challenges threaten their political survival and interests (Chime-Nganya and Ezegwu, 2017). One area of inadequacy in instrumentalism is its inability to explain situations where leadership arises to follow the will of the masses. This shortcoming notwithstanding, the theory of instrumentalism addresses the core of the subject matter of this study, which is ethno-nationalism and the renewed demand for Biafra (Iwara, Amaechi, and Netshandama, 2019). Furthermore, the dividing lines between people's opinion on the basis of ethnicity, becomes blurred when there is no opportunity for advancing parochial elite interests clouded as a group cause (Kanu, 2015). Applying this theory to the study, it is noted that the security gap speaks to the failure of the state to protect its sovereignty from internal and external attacks. The capacity gap gives credence to the inability of the state and its agencies to meet the socio-economic needs of the people by the way of providing essential services like job opportunities, good roads, potable water, power supply among others. The legitimacy gap takes into cognizance the people's failure to recognize the authority of the state, especially one that practices democracy (Maiangwa, 2016).

EFFECTS OF BIAFRA'S AGITATION ON ACADEMICS ACTIVITIES OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN EBONYI STATE.

1. Teaching Programme Implementation

Teaching programme implementation in Ebonyi State in particular and South-East in general has been reduced to four days per week instead of five working days because of the enforcement of the order in the area. Many lecturers and teachers cannot carry out their lecturing and teaching jobs in their respective schools due to the problem of sit at home order given in the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. It was submitted that many lecturers and teachers have been kidnapped and killed by criminal element in the zone. The sit at home order and other criminal activities in the region is affecting the job performance of lecturers and teachers in the region. Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) Teacher is an important figure in the realization of the objective of educational institution. The teacher is responsible for the training and production of manpower for the social, economic and technological advancement. Teachers are the implementers of school curriculum. Their functions include teaching, prepare lesson note and lesson plan, to evaluate the students, sets exam questions and mark answer sheets. The teachers' roles cannot be replaced in delivering of teaching programme. Because of the sit at home orders in the region many teachers as important as their roles and functions are in their schools have been prevented to carry out their work effectively. Chukindi,(2021) reported that schools, Banks, markets, motor parks and other public places were shut down, in observance of the court appearance of the leader of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB).

2. Students Learning Programme

Students schooling in the South East geopolitical zone of Nigeria are facing a lot of insecurity challenges especially the sit at home order by Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB). This sit at home order have affected the learning programme of students in the region. Many students due to the fear of been killed and kidnapped stay off school environment for days and months. Student's learning programme have been disrupted by the insecurity in the states across the zone. The insecurity problem and sit at home order made some public and private schools in the zone to officially stay off of school for some times. For example, Okeoma, Ede, & Nnachi, (2021) reported that private and missionary schools have shut down in Imo State as a result of the sit-at-home ordered by the Indigenous People of Biafra on Monday, May 31, 2021, throughout the South-East region. The schools asked the students to stay at home for the period to avoid any casualty. For instance, Okeoma, Ede, & Nnachi, (2021) reported that a message from schools run

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by the Catholic Archdiocese of Owerri asked parents to keep their children at home from Thursday, May 27, to Tuesday, June 1, 2021. The message from the Directorate of Education, Catholic Archdiocese of Owerri, read, "Leveraging on the already scheduled public holiday for tomorrow, we have considered it expedient to allow the students/pupils enjoy a longer weekend to resume on Tuesday, June 1, 2021

3. Disruption of School Examination

Examination in the region has also been affected by the sit at home order by Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB). Tertiary Institutions in the region are known for writing two examinations, first semester examination and second semester examination. Most of these examinations have been affected by the sit at home order given by Indigenous Peoples of Biafra IPOB in the region. For example, Blueprint (2021) observed that Students of Comprehensive Secondary School Nkume Njaba in Njaba local government area of Imo state suffered humiliation on Monday when they were chased of the examination hall by suspected Indigenous Peoples of Biafra (IPOB) operatives. Blueprint gathered that immediately the gunmen entered the school, they started shooting sporadically and both students and teachers who were at the time concentrating on the examination, fled the premises, leaving their belongings. Tribune online (2022) observed that the enforcement of the order in the region have rendered the South-East as one of the most unsafe and insecure regions in Nigeria. Public examinations have been disrupted, with adverse effects on the education sector.

4. Disruption of Academic Calendar

Academic calendar in the zone has been disrupted because of insecurity challenges and the Indigenous Peoples of Biafra IPOB sit at home order in the region. Academic calendar gives details of school activities for semester and session. The academic calendar discloses when to write test, examinations and when to close for the semester. The sit at home order in the region have affected academic activities of many tertiary institutions in the area. Many schools both public and private are not going to school on Mondays due to enforcement of the sit-at-home order, which IPOB had directed in all the five states in the zone. Obi (2012) submitted that some members of Indigenous Peoples Of Biafra IPOB members on Mondays would invades schools and disrupt their academic activities in most state in the south east region. (Starlitewnsng 2021) in one of the invasion in one of the south east state reported that both teachers and students scampered for safety as the gunmen shot sporadically into the air. Motorcycles belonging to some of the staff and students were set ablaze by the enforcers of the order. Also, Chukindi,(2021) reported that schools, Banks, markets, motor parks and other public places were Thursday totally shut down, in observance of the court appearance of the leader of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB). Ogunode & Ahaotu (2021) posits that continuous closure of schools by the state government in the Eastern Nigeria whenever there is any attack on educational institutions within or close to the state is also responsible for unstable academic calendar of various educational institutions in the states. Educational institutions operates on planned academic calendar which specifies the academic session, semester and weeks that school will open for teaching and learning. These academic calendar and programmes of educational institutions are poorly implemented due to closure of school which is unhealthy for the development of education because, teaching and learning and other academic activities are intermittently disrupted.

5. Brain-drain

The sit at home order and enforcement by Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) in the south east Nigeria is causing massive movement of professional teachers and lecturers from the region. One of the press released by the group read in part, "We, the global family of the Indigenous People of Biafra, ably led by the prophet of our time, Mazi Nnamdi Kanu, wish to announce once again that this year's annual Biafra Remembrance Day and candle light procession will take place on Sunday night, 30th of May, while a sit-at-home and total lockdown takes place on Monday, 31st of May, 2021, and not May 30 as earlier announced. "Every person in Biafra land is therefore, advised to observe a sit-at-home order on Monday, May 31, 2021. That day is a sacred day in Biafra land in honor of the over five million Biafrans massacred by the wicked Nigeria forces during the civil war. "There will be a total lockdown all through Biafra land on that day as we remember all our fallen heroes and heroines, including agitators, who have paid the supreme price in the course of our struggle for independence since 1967 till date. "All markets, filling stations, motor parks, airports, seaports, banks, schools, etc. as well as social activities in Biafra land are to be shut down on that day. Everyone is to remain indoors in Biafra land from 6am to 6pm on that day. The implication of these directives and other criminal activities by kidnappers and unknown gunmen is responsible for movement of people from the region and has posted security threat to their lives and proprieties in the region. Many teachers and lecturers in basic schools and higher institutions are relocating from the zone due to the high rate of insecurity challenges especially the sit at home order. Tribune online (2022) confirmed that gunmen have attacked traders and commuters who flout the order across the region.

6. Funding of Education

The sit at home order by the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) in the states in the south east may also affect the funding of education especially the basic education in the region. The funding of education is link to the revenue generated in each state in the region. When the revenue increases it will affects all sector positively because allocation to sectors in the economy will also increase

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too and when the revenue generated falls, it will affect the entire sector of the economy too. Every sector of the economy is tied to the total revenue of the states. Preinune Oline (2022) submitted that Professor Chukwuma Soludo, Anambra State governor, said an estimated N19.6 billion is lost in Anambra alone during sit-at-home days. It seems that IPOB is committed to ruining the economy of the south-eastern region. Also, Prime business (2021) submitted that on September 15, 2021, Ebonyi State governor and chairman, Southeast Governors' Forum, Engr. Dave Umahi, stated that the Southeast cumulatively loses N10 billion for every sit-at-home Monday enforced by the Pro Biafran Movement.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Education is very important to the overall development of the Nation. Education is not a sector to be toyed with because of its relevance to the socio-economic and technological advancement of a country. The recent insecurity challenges in the south east geo-political zone are affecting the entire educational system in the zone. This paper looked at the effects of indigenous people of Biafra agitation on tertiary institution in Ebonyi State using Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic Unwana as a study area. The paper concluded that the agitation especially the sit at home order has impacted negatively on the academic activities seriously. Some of the effects include disruption of teaching programme implementation, students learning programme, school examinations, academic calendar, brain-drain and finally the sit at home order may affect the funding of education. Based on these implications, the paper recommended that

- For peace to be built and sustained in the South East and Nigeria in general, the federal government should endeavour to have a discussion with the IPOB leaders. Using force on them should not be encouraged at all.
- Mr. President should use his good office to explore the "civil remedy" in the best interest of the people of the South East, whose economic and social life has been greatly crippled on account of the continued detention of Mazi Nnamdi Kanu. Releasing Mazi Nnamdi
- In order to reduce political instability, the nation should hold a referendum on IPOB's request for self-determinations.
- Saturday schooling should be revoked to cushion the effect of the agitation in the state.
- Federal Government should adhere to federal character principle in political appointments.
- True federalism should be practiced in Nigeria by the federal government in order to carry all the ethnic groups along because Nigeria is vast.

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